

The V International Scientific Forum “Nuclear Science and Technologies”

Monday, 7 October 2024 - Friday, 11 October 2024

Almaty, Kazakhstan

Book of Abstracts

9 октября (среда)
Утреннее заседание (09.30 – 13.00)
Секция 2 – «Энергетика и материаловедение»
Зал «Абай-холл»

Председатели:
Асет Шаймерденов, Чингис Даулбаев

1.	СТРУКТУРА И ДИНАМИКА ИНТЕРПОЛИМЕРНЫХ КОМПЛЕКСОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОЛИ-2-АЛКИЛ-2-ОКСАЗОЛИНОВ С ПОЛИКАРБОНОВЫМИ КИСЛОТАМИ <i>Yulia Gorshkova</i> ОИЯИ, Россия	09.30- 09.45
2.	TL AND EPR DATING OF POLUTEPE ARCHEOLOGICAL SITE IN AZERBAIJAN (онлайн) <i>Sahib Mammadov</i> Ministry of Science and Education, Азербайджан	09.45- 10.00
3.	PRESSURE-INDUCED PHASE TRANSITIONS IN THE COFE ₂ O ₄ AND ZN _{0.34} FE _{2.53} [] _{0.13} O ₄ FERRITES <i>Anton Rutkauskas</i> ОИЯИ, Россия	10.00- 10.15
4.	CONTROL OF THE SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNET POSITIONED ON THE DN-12 DIFFRACTOMETER OF THE IBR-2 REACTOR <i>Alexey Altynov</i> ОИЯИ, Россия	10.15- 10.30
5.	ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РАДИАЦИОННО-КАТАЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ НАНО- γ -Al ₂ O ₃ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПОЛУЧЕНИЯ ВОДОРОДА ИЗ ГЕКСАНА И СМЕСИ ГЕКСАН-ВОДА (онлайн) <i>Sevinj Melikova</i> Ministry of Science and Education, Азербайджан	10.30- 10.45

TL and EPR dating of Polutepe Archaeological Site in Azerbaijan

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Polutepe is the largest Neolithic-Eneolithic monument in the Caucasus. It is located on the eastern outskirts of Uchtepe village of Jalilabad region, Azerbaijan Republic, on the right (southern) bank of the Injachai river (39°19' 37. 67" N, 48° 27' 05.71" E) at 38 m above sea level. In this work, EPR and TL methods were used to determine the age of archaeological artifacts found at the archaeological site of Polutepe (Azerbaijan). The results of radiocarbon dating for the same site have been published else-where [1][2]. A charcoal sample excavated at the Polutepe site was dated by the conventional radi-ocarbon method at 4,270±160 BC.

The quartz inclusion method is employed for the TL dating. The quartz samples used in this experiment were extracted from ceramics using conventional chemical separation. Plotting the TL glow-curve intensity at 375°C against the dose adsorbed and backward extrapolation enables the estimated historical dose to equal 22.19±1.36 Gy. Soil sample collected from the proximity of the pottery sample was air-dried and kept in a closed environment for one month. U, Th, and K concentrations were 2.24±0.20 ppm, 8.31±0.80 ppm, and 2.39±0.23%, respectively. Dose rate and age calculation were conducted using the [DRAC version 1.2](#), and output results are as follows: Environmental dose rate: 3.46±0.19 Gy/ka and; Age of the sample: 6,400±530 BC years.

The investigated object for the EPR investigations was the presumable lower jaw of a caw with a well-preserved tooth. [ROSY software](#) was used to calculate the enamel sample's age A by comparing accumulated archaeological dose (Da) to the average dose rate (D) over such a period: $A=Da/D$. The calculation of D was based on the estimated cosmic dose rate and U, Th, and K content obtained from soil sample analysis. The cosmic dose rate was determined to be 119 microGy/a. The average moisture content of the sediment was taken as 15% on the bases of measurement at the site. Uranium concentration determined directly in the tooth enamel was less than the detection limit; therefore, the possible uranium uptake was not considered. The total estimated annual dose rate was equal to 1,543 microGy/a. The mean age of the sample was determined as 7,770 ± 130 years

Keywords: ESR dating, TL dating, tooth enamel, pottery

References

- [1] S. Mammadov, East Eur. J. Phys. 2024, 2024 (1), 442–446. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26565/2312-4334-2024-1-48>. [2] S. Mammadov, M. Gurbanov, L. Ahmadzade, A. Abishov, Radiat. Phys. Chem. 2024, 219 (October 2023), 111650. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2024.111650>.